

The Collapse Of Carillion

A Case Study In Corporate Governance

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INTRODUCTION

It caught most people involved by surprise when Carillion underwent rapid organisational disassembly and dissolution. Employees, contractors, suppliers, customers, governments, and society in general, would be forgiven to assume that a company grounded in exacting engineering standards to execute its construction business, stringent government procurement scrutiny it needs to adhere to, and the demanding citizen services it is tasked to fulfil would approach the governance and management of its business with a level of discipline and integrity aligned with the essence of its main business proposition. Carillion's fall became a cautionary tale of how neglect and corruption from just a few stakeholders within its governance structure can trigger disastrous outcomes for the business. But the argument of this essay relates to factors and responsibilities of managing agents and stakeholders that were either neglected or were deliberately fraudulent. This enabled corruption at the highest level despite the defined corporate governance required from a leading and publicly listed corporation in the UK.

This paper will examine a brief outline of the circumstances and surrounding environment in which Carillion operated. We take stock of the opportunities it pursued and the constraints it had to manage in addition to corporate governance factors that precipitated its decline. Next, we will map and correlate corporate governance realities and failings with the corporate structure and behaviours to understand the theories that were relevant. Finally, we conclude with the crucial investigations and learnings derived from Carillion's downfall, especially from the perspective of the UK government which was its most crucial customer as well as future engagement regarding the provision of critical infrastructure and services that the wider society relies upon.

TIMELINE OF EVENTS

Before its collapse in 2018, Carillion was the second-largest construction company in the UK. The company employed around 43,000 workers, 19,000 of them in the UK alone (House of Commons, 2018). Carillion's contracts extended beyond the UK and include the Middle East,

the Caribbean, and Canada. The company's projects encompass both the public and private sectors. It has extensive projects for the UK government which range from building roads, and hospitals, running prison estates, providing school meals, participating in the development of HS2, defence infrastructure, and facilities management. In its 2016 report, 38% of the company's revenues are from projects for the UK government alone (House of Commons, 2018).

Carillion was formed in 1999 after it demerged from Tarmac (National Archive, 2022). It is primarily a construction company but it rapidly expanded its services and growth through a series of ambitious and aggressive mergers and acquisitions (Mor et al, 2018). The company purchased major rivals such as Mowlem, Alfred McAlpine, and Eaga. By acquiring other companies and diversifying, Carillion eliminated competitors for major contracts and moved into areas where it has no apparent operating competence and expertise (Mabbet, 2018). Carillion's acquisitions and expansion have been an unbridled pursuit of growth which lack coherent plans for its long-term sustainability or impact on its employees, pensioners, and suppliers. Mergers and acquisitions were funded by raising debt and this unsustainable business model is a disaster waiting to unfold (Mor et al, 2018; Trades Union Congress, 2018).

COLLAPSE

From a seeming position of strength and stability, Carillion, a major UK construction and facilities management company providing vital services to the government entered into compulsory liquidation in January 2018 (House of Commons, 2018; The Insolvency Service, 2018).

While bankruptcies and corporate failures are an inevitable part of the business cycle, the collapse of Carillion is a very unusual case (House of Commons, 2018; Sadan, 2018). Firstly, Carillion's collapse was sudden. Publicly available reports show that the company is in a stable financial position. Prior to its liquidation, the company paid a record dividend of £79m and generous compensations have been given to senior executives (House of Commons, 2018). Secondly, as a publicly listed company in the UK Carillion is required to undergo audits.

KPMG served as Carillion's auditors since its founding in 1999. During that period, all audits published were certified true and fair by KPMG (Mor et al, 2018; Trades Union Congress, 2018). Lastly, Carillion is a major strategic supplier to the UK government with hundreds of contracts in their pipeline (Mor et al, 2018). It has established itself as a key player in the construction industry both in the UK and overseas and has been involved in some of the most high-profile infrastructure projects. The UK government has a stringent vetting process for engaging with companies, especially in the sector where Carillion is heavily involved (Cabinet Office, 2012). Several warnings have been raised to the government about potential "trigger events" in Carillion that could lead to financial distress but no decisive action has been done by respective government offices (House of Commons, 2018; Sasse et al, 2022).

The collapse of Carillion is a result of systemic corruption and corporate governance failure. Its board and top executives failed to provide a transparent accounting of the company's transactions and only seek to enrich themselves with generous corporate bonuses (Mabbet, 2018; Sasse et al, 2020; Sadan, 2018; Trades Union Congress, 2018). A company-wide corruption and mismanagement proliferated where the executives, board members, internal auditors, and external auditors are all complicit and chose to turn a blind eye to the issues raised without any regard for the wider stakeholders of the company (House of Commons, 2018, Mor et al, 2018).

Carillion's sudden downfall is also a government failure. The construction and engineering industry of which Carillion is a major player requires stringent certifications and regulations to be followed (Cabinet Office, 2012). In fact, there are extensive policies, strategies, standards, and operating guidelines pertaining to construction, project management, finance management, and risk management that all interplay in the successful initiation, implementation, delivery, issue resolution, and maintenance (Infrastructure & Projects Authority, 2021). Construction is viewed as a crucial element of the growth of the economy; codified policies and extensive cross-discipline strategies are in place to ensure the clarity of its importance (Department for Business, Innovation & Skills, 2013; Infrastructure & Projects Authority, 2016). In the case of Carillion which is a provider of critical government services, stricter frameworks and regulations must be adhered to before it can even qualify for a contract

(Davies et al, 2018). A system of checks and balances on the government's side for major contractors like Carillion failed to make any decisive actions and allowed lapses to proliferate despite the early warning signs (House of Commons, 2018). In addition and contrary to expectations, the margins that the private sector earns from public contracts are very minimal and providers are often faced with cost overruns (Mabbet, 2018). The government needs to overhaul its audit, procurement practices, and management of high-risk, large-scale contracts to prevent another Carillion from happening in the future (Davies et al, 2018; Sasse, 2020).

Table 01 - Timeline of key events in Carillion's lifetime (House of Commons, 2018; Mor et al, 2018; Trades Union Congress, 2018)

Date	Event
2006 February	Acquisition of Mowlem for £350 million
2008 February	Acquisition of Alfred McAlpine for £565 million
2008 October	Acquisition of Vanbots Construction (Canada) for £14.3 million
2011 April	Acquisition of Ega for £298 million
2012 January	Richard Howson appointed as Chief Executive
2014 May	Philip Green appointed as Chairman
2015 July	Keith Cochrane appointed to board as Senior Independent Non-Executive Director
2017	
2017 January	Zafar Khan appointed to board as Finance Director
10 July 2017	Carillion announced a thorough review of its business and capital structure and the £845 million contract provision
12 July 2017	Carillion's (LSE: CLLN) share value fell 70% after its July 10th announcement
11 September 2017	Zafar Khan removed as Finance Director and Emma Mercer appointed as his replacement. Appointment of new non-executive directors.
29 September 2017	Announcement of half-year results which included a further £200 million profit write down
17 November 2017	Third profit warning is issued alongside announcement that the company was heading towards a breach of its debt covenants
31 December 2017	Carillion submitted a formal request for Government support
2018	
13 January 2018	The company sent a letter to Cabinet Office making a final request of £160 million including and immediate £10 million
14 January 2018	Cabinet Office informed the company that it would not be willing to provide such support to the company The board concluded that the company was insolvent
15 January 2018	Directors presented a petition to the Court for the compulsory winding up of the company on the grounds it was unable to pay its debts Government announced they were making £150 million available to support the liquidation and laying a contingent liability to indemnify the Official Receiver Carillion issued a notice to the London Stock Exchange: "that it had no choice but to take steps to enter into compulsory liquidation with immediate effect" 6 UK Carillion businesses liquidated in first phase including Carillion plc and Carillion Construction Ltd
End of 2018	All of 91 Carillion companies had been liquidated

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE FAILURES

The aftermath of Carillion's liquidation has left profound and lasting impacts both in the UK and overseas. It severely affected the construction industry and triggered a series of insolvencies and bankruptcies of thousands of other smaller businesses comprising Carillion's supply chain. At the time of its collapse, there are 75,000 workers involved in its supply chain in addition to its 43,000 employees. (Neate & Davies, 2020). While some of these workers were relocated to other companies, the majority of them faced uncertainty in their livelihood and pension. This event also left a deep political impact in the UK. As a major contractor of the government, Carillion's sudden collapse stymied vital and critical government projects; i.e. hospitals for the NHS, HS2 and other transportation infrastructure, school buildings, etc. A parliamentary investigation has been conducted which resulted in a thorough review of corporate governance, contracting, procurement, accounting and audit practices in the UK and calls to reform existing laws and regulations (Sasse et al, 2020; Trades Union Congress, 2020).

The UK Parliament report concluded that Carillion's board is responsible and culpable for its demise (House of Commons, 2018). Investigations into the company showed that the board failed in various aspects of the business:

- There is a prevalent and systemic culture of corruption in Carillion as evidenced by its fraudulent and questionable accounting and financial practices. The board misrepresented the reality of the business and deceived its investors, employees, and suppliers by presenting a position of stability and growth to its stakeholders when it is nonexistent in reality (Mor et al, 2018).
- The auditors and accountants were complicit in this deception. Despite having the Big Four (KPMG, Deloitte, EY, PwC) auditing firms at their service, not a single issue was raised about Carillion's finances and all of the auditors acquiesced to its aggressive accounting methods. Any shortcomings in the company's financials were deliberately ignored.

- The board and executives placed great importance on dividends and bonuses despite the red flags and warning signs in the company's financials such as rising debts and growing deficits.
- There is a lack of transparency between the board and the company's shareholders. Misleading reports and audits were provided which prevented the shareholders from influencing board decision-making.

The UK has a considerably well-developed and mature system of corporate governance and business regulations (Cadbury, 1992; Cheffins, 2013). As highlighted in the Cadbury Report, "Corporate governance is concerned with *holding the balance* between economic & social goals and between individual & communicable goals" with the aim of aligning all the interests of individuals, corporations, and society. However, aligning and balancing the competing interests of the shareholders and directors of a company is always a challenging task in practice (Blair & Stout, 2001; Stout, 2012). UK's corporate governance system places greater weight on shareholder primacy (Armour et al, 2003; Trades Union Congress, 2018). The extent that Carillion placed on shareholder primacy and maximising its shareholder value drove it to pursue risky financial tactics which eventually contributed to its downfall (Mabbet, 2018).

Carillion was a perfect illustration of agency theory which shows how executives and managers interested only in pursuing their self-interests deceived their investors and focused only on short-termism, which eventually brought about the company's demise (Clarke, 2004; Palladino & Karlsson, 2019; Stout, 2012). As a publicly listed company, Carillion is under constant scrutiny by the stock market. It needs to present growth which is primarily driven by its relentless acquisitions rather than improving and developing its existing services (Mabbet, 2018; Stout, 2012).

The sector of Carillion's operations: construction and engineering, requires it to deal with an extensive and complex supply chain in order to complete a project. This aspect of corporate governance demonstrates resource dependency theory (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978) wherein an organisation engages or negotiates with other organisations or environments in order to acquire the resources it needs. One objective is for the organisation to be able to cope

with or reduce uncertainty, especially when working with complex products and services in demanding environments (Clarke, 2004). In the case of Carillion, instead of forging mutually beneficial and advantageous partnerships with its suppliers, the opposite happened. The directors and executives ailed to reduce uncertainty and risk in the firm. At the time of its collapse, Carillion owed around £2 billion to its almost 30,000 suppliers; the result of its constant manipulation and exploitation of suppliers (House of Commons, 2018).

Table 02 - Applicability Of Corporate Governance Theories To Carillion (Alchian & Demsetz, 1972; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978; Stout, 2012)

Theory	Applicability To Carillion	Remarks
Shareholder Primacy Theory	Yes	The company paid out more dividends than the cash they generated. Directors are determined to increase dividends paid each year despite increased borrowing and deficits.
Agency Theory	Yes	The Board and Executives acted on their own self-interest and ignored the long-term sustainability of the company, its employees, and suppliers
Resource Dependency Theory	Yes	Company requires an extensive supply chain to deliver complex infrastructure projects
Stewardship Theory	No	There is a collective failure of stewardship responsibilities of Carillion's management. There is lack of transparency between board members and investors. This in turn resulted in investors divesting from the company.

AFTERMATH

Carillion, as one of the biggest engineering and construction companies in the UK, is not building trivial projects or doing cosmetic repairs only. It is involved in a considerable number of high-profile projects and is a strategic and critical supplier of services for the Government; there is no reason for this collapse to happen. When big companies fail, it is always easy to pin the blame on the executives and directors and while Carillion's management is clearly

responsible, the role of the government in preventing this collapse and its consequences cannot be overlooked. The corporate governance, regulations and monitoring frameworks are not lacking but this needs to be coupled with rigorous implementation in order to be effective.

Carillion's collapse has called for a reform of existing procurement, audit, and supplier management practices of the government. It also exposed the shortcomings in the accounting and auditing practices of businesses in the UK. While action and reforms are being implemented, the environment that enabled Carillion's unsustainable practices to continue is still in existence and its collapse remains to have far-reaching consequences. Carillion's collapse and failings are more than just a failure of corporate governance and concrete actions must be taken by both the private and public sectors in order to prevent another catastrophe like this from happening.

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